

ABSTRACT

This descriptive research determined the level of compliance in the implementation of the risk reduction and disaster preparedness program. The study was conducted among 17 elementary and secondary school heads and 17 school DRRM Coordinators of Schools District of Ajuy-Cluster II. Research instrument used was the standardized tool formulated by the Department of Education in its School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Manual (2012). Statistical tools were mean, standard deviation and Mann-Whitney U Test. Significance level for inferential test was set at 0.05 alpha. Findings of the study revealed that the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of Enabling Environment pillar was *fully complied* when taken as a whole and grouped according to the designation while as to the type of school, elementary was *fully complied* and secondary was *partially complied*. In terms of Safe Learning Facilities pillar, the implementation was *fully complied* when taken as a whole and grouped according to the type of school while as to designation, school head was *fully complied* and school DRRM coordinators was *partially complied*. For School Disaster Management and Risk Reduction and Resilience Education pillar respondents were *partially complied* when taken as a whole and grouped according to the type of school and designation. Moreover, a significant difference existed in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of enabling environment pillar when they were grouped according to the type of school. Meanwhile, when they were grouped according to the designation there was no significant difference. In addition, there were no significant differences as well in terms of safe learning facilities, school disaster management, and risk reduction and resilience education pillar when grouped according to the type of school and designation. The School Disaster Management pillar shows the lowest mean. Thus, this pillar was the focus of the proposed strategic action plan.

Keywords: *Disaster preparedness, pandemic, risk reduction, strategic action plan*

INTRODUCTION

Schools under the Department of Education were one of the institutions that experienced the threats brought by this COVID-19 global pandemic. The closure of schools on the advent of this crisis challenged the Philippine education system on its preparedness in this kind of threat. The absence of policies, procedures, and protocols in dealing with such a global pandemic made the education sector exposed to danger and risk. Thus, for the safety of personnel and learners, schools were closed.

The current scenario needs serious attention to disaster capacity and mitigation efforts to reduce exposure and vulnerability in international and local settings. Disasters like this global pandemic are inevitable, but their scope and magnitude are often magnified due to unsustainable development that has not taken into account the possible hazard impacts. In the Schools Division of Iloilo, the schools and learning centers faced this health threat unarmed. At the onset of the global pandemic, there is no contingency plan or policy directives as to the protocols to be observed during these times. Without the actual level of compliance from the core thematic areas of the risk reduction and disaster preparedness program, no strategic or action plan were formulated in dealing with and combating this kind of threat

DepEd Memorandum No. 15, series of 2020, is known as the “First Set of Policy Directives of the DepEd Task Force COVID-19”. Measures for the prevention and control of the COVID-19 in Basic Education Schools and Offices were stated. Also, formation and activation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Teams in all DepEd offices and safety precautions and protocols were established.

The disasters experienced in the Philippines spurred the DepEd (Department of Education) authorities to integrate disaster risk reduction and management in their curricula. Section 14 of Republic Act 10121 (or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010) requires the DepEd among other agencies to integrate the said curricula. For the elementary and junior high school levels, DRRM (Disaster Risk Reduction and Management) education has not been made a stand-alone subject but only a component of subjects such as science, technology, and social science. The DepEd, however, has made DRRM education an independent subject for the senior high school level.

These persuasive factors prompted the researchers to conduct the study which aimed to describe the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in the aspects of enabling environment, safe learning facilities, school disaster management,

and risk reduction and resilience education amidst the pandemic among public schools in the District of Ajuy cluster II, Division of Iloilo as basis for the development of a Strategic Action Plan that will provide a comprehensive school safety measures whenever untoward health threats or pandemic may arise.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The descriptive method of research was used in this study to determine the level of compliance among public schools in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness. The data gathered in this study were analyzed and interpreted using the Mean, Standard Deviation, and Mann Whitney U Test as statistical tools. All statistical computations were tallied, classified, analyzed and processed through the use of a statistical software.

Participants/Respondents. The participants were the 17 elementary and secondary school heads and 17 school DRRM Coordinators of Schools District of Ajuy- Cluster II. To gather more specific information on the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program, the researchers used the standardized tool formulated by the Department of Education in its School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Manual (2012).

Data Analysis Procedure. The data gathered in this study were analyzed and interpreted using the Mean, Standard Deviation, and Mann Whitney U Test as statistical tools. All statistical computations were tallied, classified, analyzed and processed through the use of a statistical software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness Level of Compliance in terms of Enabling Environment Pillar

Table 1 shows that when the gathered data was taken as an entire group the implementation on the risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of enabling environment pillar was “fully complied” (M=2.53, SD=.514). Meanwhile, when grouped according to the type of school, results revealed that elementary school was “fully complied” (M=2.75, SD=.452) while secondary school was “partially complied” (M=2.00, SD=.000).

Moreover, result shows that when taken as to the designation both school DRRM coordinator (M=2.59, SD=.507) and school head (M=2.65, SD=.493) were “fully complied”. This means that both the school heads and school DRRM coordinators fully practiced and complied with the function Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Enabling Environment Pillar.

Table 1. *Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Enabling Environment Pillar*

Category	SD	Mean	Description
Entire Group	0.514	2.53	Fully Complied
Type of School			
Elementary	0.452	2.75	Fully Complied
Secondary	0.000	2.00	Partially Complied
Designation			
School DRRM Coordinator	0.507	2.59	Fully Complied
School Head	0.493	2.65	Fully Complied

*Note: 2.34-3.00, Fully Complied; 1.67-2.33, Partially Complied; 1.00-1.66, Not-complied

Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness Level of Compliance in terms of Safe Learning Facilities Pillar

As revealed in Table 2, level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness were “fully complied” in terms of safe learning facilities pillar when they were taken as a whole ($M=2.53$, $SD=.514$) and when grouped according to the type of school, elementary ($M=2.50$, $SD=.522$) and secondary schools ($M=2.60$, $SD=.548$).

Moreover, when grouped as to the designation, result shows that school DRRM coordinator was “partially complied” ($M=2.35$, $SD=.493$) and the school head was “fully complied” ($M=2.59$, $SD=.507$).

Table 2. Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Safe Learning Facilities Pillar

Category	SD	Mean	Description
Entire Group	0.514	2.53	Fully Complied
Type of School			
Elementary	0.522	2.50	Fully Complied
Secondary	0.548	2.60	Fully Complied
Designation			
School DRRM Coordinator	0.493	2.35	Partially Complied
School Head	0.507	2.59	Fully Complied

*Note: 2.34-3.00, Fully Complied; 1.67-2.33, Partially Complied; 1.00-1.66, Not-complied

Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness Level of Compliance in terms of School Disaster Management Pillar

Table 3 shows that the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of school disaster management pillar were “partially complied” when respondents were taken as a whole ($M=2.18$, $SD=.393$) and when grouped according to the type of school, elementary school ($M=2.25$, $SD=.452$) and secondary school ($M=2.00$, $SD=.000$) and according to the designation, school DRRM coordinator ($M=2.29$, $SD=.588$) and school head ($M=2.29$, $SD=.470$).

Table 3. Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of School Disaster Management Pillar

Category	SD	Mean	Description
Entire Grouped	0.393	2.18	Partially Complied
Type of School			
Elementary	0.452	2.25	Partially Complied
Secondary	0.000	2.00	Partially Complied
Designation			Partially Complied
School DRRM Coordinator	0.588	2.29	Partially Complied
School Head	0.470	2.29	Partially Complied

*Note: 2.34-3.00, Fully Complied; 1.67-2.33, Partially Complied; 1.00-1.66, Not-complied

Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness Level of Compliance in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience Education Pillar

As shown in Table 4, the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of risk reduction and resilience education pillar were “partially complied” when respondents were taken as a whole ($M=2.29$, $SD=.470$) and when grouped according to the type of school, elementary school ($M=2.42$, $SD=.515$) and secondary school ($M=2.00$, $SD=.000$). Meanwhile, according to the designation, school DRRM coordinator ($M=2.41$, $SD=.618$) was also “partially complied” while the school head ($M=2.53$, $SD=.514$) was “fully complied”.

Table 4. *Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience in Education Pillar*

Category	SD	Mean	Description
Entire Grouped	0.470	2.29	Partially Complied
Type of School			
Elementary	0.515	2.42	Partially Complied
Secondary	0.000	2.00	Partially Complied
Designation			Partially Complied
School DRRM Coordinator	0.618	2.41	Partially Complied
School Head	0.514	2.53	Fully Complied

**Note: 2.34-3.00, Fully Complied; 1.67-2.33, Partially Complied; 1.00-1.66, Not-complied*

Differences in the Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Enabling Environment Pillar

A significant difference existed in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of enabling environment pillar when grouped according to the type of school, ($z=2.739$, $p=0.006$, $p < .05$). This implies that the type of school matters in the success of the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of enabling environment pillar.

Meanwhile, there was no significant difference in the level of compliance in the implementation when they were grouped according to the designation, ($z= 0.348$, $p=0.728$, $p < .05$). Table 5 shows the data.

Table 5. *Mann-Whitney U Test Result of the Difference in the Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Enabling Environment Pillar when they were grouped according to Type of School and Designation*

Category	z-value	p-value	Decision
Type of School	2.739	0.006	Significant
Designation	0.348	0.728	Not Significant

**p < .05*

Differences in the Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Safe Learning Facilities Pillar

As shown in table 6, there was no significant difference in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of safe learning facilities pillar when respondents were grouped according to the type of school, ($z=0.365$, $p=0.715$, $p < .05$) and designation, ($z=1.354$, $p=0.176$, $p < .05$).

Table 6. *Mann-Whitney U Test Result of the Difference in the Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Safe Learning Facilities Pillar when they were grouped according to Type of School and Designation*

Category	z-value	p-value	Decision
Type of School	0.365	0.715	Not Significant
Designation	1.354	0.176	Not Significant

* $p < .05$

Differences in the Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of School Disaster Management Pillar

As revealed in table 7, there was no significant difference in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of school disaster management pillar when they were grouped according to the type of school, ($z=1.195$, $p=0.232$, $p < .05$) and designation, ($z=0.103$, $p=0.918$, $p < .05$).

Table 7. *Mann-Whitney U Test Result of the Difference in the Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of School Disaster Management Pillar when they were grouped according to Type of School and Designation*

Category	z-value	p-value	Decision
Type of School	1.195	0.232	Not Significant
Designation	0.103	0.918	Not Significant

* $p < .05$

Differences in the Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience in Education Pillar

Table 8 shows that there was no significant difference in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program in terms of risk reduction and resilience education pillar when they were grouped according to the type of school, ($z=1.667$, $p=0.096$, $p < .05$) and designation, ($z=0.490$, $p=0.624$, $p < .05$).

Table 8. *Mann-Whitney U Test Result of the Difference in the Level of Compliance in the implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience in Education Pillar when they were grouped according to Type of School and Designation*

Category	z-value	p-value	Decision
Type of School	1.667	0.096	Not Significant
Designation	0.490	0.624	Not Significant

* $p < .05$

Summary of the Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of the Four Pillars

As shown in table 9, the pillar with the lowest mean in the level of compliance in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program was the school disaster management pillar with a mean score of 2.18. Thus, this pillar has been the focus in the proposed strategic action plan as an offshoot of the study.

Table 9. *Level of Compliance in the Implementation of Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness in terms of the Four Pillars as basis for the development of Strategic Action Plan*

Pillars	M	Description	Rank
Enabling Environment	2.53	Fully Complied	1
Safe Learning Facilities	2.53	Fully Complied	2
Risk Reduction & Resilience Education	2.29	Partially Complied	3
School Disaster Management	2.18	Partially Complied	4

**Note: 2.34-3.00, Fully Complied; 1.67-2.33, Partially Complied; 1.00-1.66, Not-complied*

PROPOSED STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN

I. Rationale

The Philippines is exposed to various natural and human-induced hazards. In times of disasters, education is one of the most vulnerable sectors. Disasters often disrupt learning and the normal operations of schools and DepEd offices; they also threaten and affect both the lives of learners and personnel and other educational resources and investments.

II. Purpose

To increase the level of compliance of the schools in the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of the School Disaster Management Pillar.

III. Objectives

1. To empower the learners, personnel, schools and offices to ensure safety and learning continuity;
2. Institutionalize Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM), Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Education in Emergencies (EiE) in the scope of work across and within all levels of DepEd;
3. and strengthen the resilience of K-12 education in the context of natural and human-induced hazards.

❖ School Contingency Planning and Preparedness Plan turned into response actions when a disaster or pandemic strikes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training-workshop on crafting the School Contingency Plan ✓ Presentation of the School Contingency Plan to various stakeholders ✓ Simulation of the School Contingency Plan
❖ Establishment of school personnel and learners tracking system/ protocol in the event of a disaster or emergency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Data-gathering of school personnel and learners ✓ Encoding/ Processing of raw data into a digital database and readily-available hard copies ✓ Establishment of tracking system/ protocol in the event of a disaster or emergency
❖ Posting of Hazard and evacuation maps in conspicuous places in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Crafting and development of hazard (<i>earthquake, fire, flood, typhoon</i>) and evacuation (<i>violent intruders</i>) maps ✓ Identifying conspicuous places in the school ✓ Use approved and available Information Education and Communication (IEC) materials from local and national agencies or the DepEd DRRM Service ✓ Posting of Hazard and evacuation maps in conspicuous places in the school
❖ Provision of first aid kit in every instructional classroom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Request to Purchase items for first aid kit ✓ Procurement of first aid kit ✓ Distribution/provision of first aid kits
❖ Provision of at least 2 necessary and functioning equipment, in case of a disaster (e.g. fire extinguisher, handheld/base radio, generator, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Request to Purchase items for emergency equipment ✓ Procurement of emergency equipment ✓ Distribution/provision of emergency equipment
❖ Conduct regular hazard-specific drills (at least 3 hazards) with the participation of stakeholders (BFP, Medic, LGUs, NGOs, community, PTA, alumni, and others)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training-Workshop on how to properly conduct hazard-specific drills (earthquake, fire & flood) ✓ Simulation/practicum ✓ Conduct hazard-specific drills with collaboration with the BFP, Medic, LGUs, NGOs, community, PTA, alumni, and others
❖ Establishment of functional early warning system to inform students and personnel of hazards and emergencies (protocol, warning signs, devices, IEC), considering national and LGU warning systems and protocols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Develop innovative ways how to establish functional early warning systems such as the use of social media, short messaging service (SMS), flag-warning system, bell-warning system, etc.
❖ Training of personnel to administer first aid to students and personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training-workshop on administering first aid to students and personnel (it includes bandaging, CPR, and carrying) ✓ Simulation/Practicum
❖ Pre-identification of Temporary Learning spaces/Shelters in the aftermath of a disaster or emergency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Conduct assessment on the possible area to be identified as Temporary Learning space/shelter ✓ Provision of readily-available Temporary Learning Space materials such as tents, ropes, and other materials needed
❖ Crafting of Education Continuity Plan (in times of disaster, emergencies, and pandemics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training-workshop on crafting the Education Continuity Plan ✓ Presentation of the Education Continuity Plan to various stakeholders ✓ Simulation of the Education Continuity Plan
❖ Psychosocial interventions for personnel and students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Conduct survey and assessment on the number of personnel and students that need psychosocial intervention ✓ Conduct psychosocial intervention to identified learners and personnel ✓ Conduct psychosocial debriefing activities
❖ Training of teachers and other personnel who could provide psychosocial support to students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training-workshop on Psychosocial Support to students
❖ Conduct awareness and capacity building for families and learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Awareness and capacity building for families and learners

❖ Participation in the different Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) activities of the LGU	✓ School actively participates in the different Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) activities of the LGU
--	---

IV. Suggested Strategies/Activities

To carry out the programs in the School Disaster Management pillar, these are the suggested activities to guide its operation.

The proposed strategic action plan was composed of the following parts: 1) goals and objectives or targets; 2) strategies or activities; 3) resources needed; 4) persons involved; 5) sources of fund; 6) budgetary requirements; 7) target date; and 8) expected outcomes or output. However, for the purpose of the publication of this paper the following parts were only included.

CONCLUSION

In view of the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: The schools in the District of Ajuy cluster 2 were partially complied with the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness program during the pandemic. This was a manifestation that the authorities in the basic education sector have made inroads in their efforts towards resilience-building in offices and schools, and ensuring that quality education is continuously provided and prioritized even during disasters and emergencies. However, there are still a lot of things to do so that schools can fully complied with the implementation.

School heads and school DRRM coordinators in both elementary and secondary schools observed and practiced full compliance in terms of enabling environment pillar. It means that policies relating to Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in education and school safety were adopted. School DRRM team was also formed with defined membership and roles and functions. Schools have a comprehensive school disaster risk reduction and management plan in emergency measures like a global pandemic. In the financial aspect, the school budget supports DRRM activities. Data collection, consolidation, and reporting to monitor results and impact was also evident. This manifest a well-maintained partnership the schools were able to tap to support its DRRM programs.

School heads and school DRRM coordinators in both elementary and secondary schools observed and practiced full compliance in terms of the safe learning facilities pillar. This demonstrates that schools adhere to the National Building Code-approved standard designs and specifications of the school buildings and structures. Risk assessment, regular inspection, and repair of minor damages are done regularly to maintain the safety and structural integrity of school buildings.

School heads and school DRRM coordinators in both elementary and secondary schools generally observed and practiced partial compliance in terms of the school disaster risk management pillar. Schools were not able to establish tracking systems or protocols in the event of disaster or emergencies like a global pandemic. Inadequate or absence of first aid kits and emergency equipment is also evident. "Lack of training among members of the faculty" remains a constant problem in the implementation of risk reduction and management programs.

School heads and school DRRM coordinators in both elementary and secondary schools generally observed and practiced partial compliance in terms of risk reduction in the education pillar. The role of DRRM programs in school is to provide enough knowledge and information to teachers. Due to the lack of interest and knowledge in the subject, teachers often feel reluctant to give priority to disaster-related topics of curriculum, and most of the time; this was not taught to the students in their academic sessions.

The type of school matters in the success of the implementation of risk reduction and disaster preparedness in terms of enabling environment pillar. The DepEd has a repository of learning materials but no specific training materials for disaster risk reduction management. They just incorporated it into existing subjects, and they had minimal training materials for the teachers. The lack of learning and other materials continues to burden teachers and students alike so much so that even DepEd officials have bemoaned this shortage of materials besetting the country's public schools.

REFERENCES

- Asian Disaster Reduction Center (2002). ADRC 20th Century Asian Natural Disasters Data Book. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/H18EkU>, (accessed last 17 November 2021).
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, US: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Benson, C. (2016). Promoting Sustainable Development through Disaster risk management. Metro Manila, Philippines. Asian Development Bank. Retrieved from: <https://goo.gl/4AmtqJ>, (accessed last 25 November 2021).
- Borromeo, Robert A., Babila, Jolly S., Orbon, Myrtle, Paez, Winifredo C., Estapon, Natividad D., Gayoba, Arlene M. (2017). Determining the Disaster Preparedness of Students and Non-teaching Employees of Adventist University of the Philippines (AUP) and Its Financial implications. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/DoWfLj>, (accessed last 3 November 2021).
- Commission on Audit (2016, February 1) Consolidated Report on the Audit of the Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Fund for the year ended December 31, 2014. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/NmC7gE>, (accessed last 27 November 2021).
- Department of Education. (2012). *School Disaster Risk reduction and Management Manual*. Pasig, Metro Manila: Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Service. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/VDfH5Z>, (accessed last 9 November 2021).
- Esteban, M., Valenzuela, V. P., Yun, N. Y., Mikami, T., Shibayama, T., Matsumaru, R., ... & Nakamura, R. (2015). Typhoon Haiyan 2013 evacuation preparations and awareness. *International Journal of sustainable Future for Human Security*, 3(1), 37-45. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/99kkDn>, (accessed last 19 November 2021).
- Hansson, S. O. (2005). *Decision theory: A brief introduction*. Stockholm, Sweden. Department of Philosophy and the History of Technology Royal Institute of Technology (KTH). Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/nZftYp>, (accessed last 20 November 2021).
- Humanitarian Response (2013, October 25). Bohol Earthquake Action Plan. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/aK4Mqi>, (accessed last 8 November 2021).
- Medina, A. (2016). Promoting a culture of disaster preparedness. *Journal of business continuity & emergency planning*, 9(3), 281-290. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/zTxeF5>, (accessed last November 2021).
- Meinardus, R. (2003). The crisis of public education in the Philippines. *Business World Internet Edition*. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/NmFm64>, (accessed last 17 November 2021).
- Muttarak, Raya and Pothisiri, Wiraporn. (2013). The Role of Education on Disaster Preparedness: Case Study of 2012 Indian Ocean Earthquakes on Thailand's Andaman Coast. *Ecology & Society*, 18 (4). pp. 1-16. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/JxQ9Ac>, (accessed last 20 November 2021).
- Parsons, M., Glavac, S., Hastings, P., Marshall, G., McGregor, J., McNeill, J., Morley, P., Reeve, I., & Stayner, R. (2016). Top-down assessment of disaster resilience: a conceptual framework using coping and adaptive capacities. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 19, 1-11. Peer Reviewed Journal 42
- Rambau, T. S., Beukes, L. D., & Fraser, W. (2012). Disaster Risk Reduction through school learners' awareness and preparedness. *Jambá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 4(1), 1-11. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/ATZ2oG>, (accessed last 27 November 2021). Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/EYo6eS>, (accessed last 21 November 2021).
- SEAMEO INNOTECH. (2014). *Toolkit for Building Disaster- Resilient School Communities in Southeast Asia*. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/un9LBM>, (accessed last 18 November 2021).

- Shaw, R., Shiwaku Hirohide Kobayashi, K., & Kobayashi, M. (2004). Linking experience, education, perception and earthquake preparedness. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 13(1), 39-49. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/zYPnMa>, (accessed last 2 November 2021).
- Sinha, A., Pal, D. K., Kasar, P. K., Tiwari, R., & Sharma, A. (2008). Knowledge, attitude and practice of disaster preparedness and mitigation among medical students. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 17(4), 503-507. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/nD6q5B>, (accessed last 1 November 2021).
- Skinner, B. F. (2014). *Contingencies of reinforcement: A theoretical analysis (Vol. 3)*. BF Skinner Foundation. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/3RfctC>, (accessed last 29 November 2021.)
- Tuladhar, G., Yatabe, R., Dahal, R. K., & Bhandary, N. P. (2015). Assessment of disaster risk reduction knowledge of school teachers in Nepal. *International Journal of Health System and Disaster Management*, 3(1), 20. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/mg998C>, (accessed last 6 November 2021).

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.